
Research

Recreation Of Mythology in J.K Rowling's *Harry Potter And The Goblet Of Fire*

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Abstract: J.K. Rowling's "Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire" transcends the realm of contemporary fantasy literature by ingeniously weaving elements of mythology into the narrative fabric. This research delves into the multifaceted layers of mythic reinvention within the fourth installment of the series. Through a comprehensive analysis of the Triwizard Tournament, mythical creatures, the resurrection of Lord Voldemort, and the overarching themes of friendship, loyalty, and destiny, this study unveils Rowling's adept fusion of timeless mythic motifs with the modern wizarding world. The symbolism embedded in the Triwizard Cup, the moral dilemmas faced by characters, and the cyclical nature of time further underscore the rich tapestry of mythic storytelling. This abstract encapsulates the intricate interplay between ancient mythologies and Rowling's contemporary narrative, highlighting how "Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire" stands as a testament to the enduring power of myth in literature.

Keywords: J.K. Rowling, Harry Potter, Goblet of Fire, mythology

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Introduction

J.K. Rowling's "Harry Potter" series has captivated readers worldwide, not merely for its enchanting narrative but for its intricate interweaving of mythology into the fabric of the wizarding world. Among the seven books in the series, "Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire" stands out as a pinnacle, exploring a deeper layer of mythological elements that contribute significantly to the overall richness of the narrative.

The usage of mythology in literature has been a longstanding tradition, serving as a means to convey cultural values, explore universal themes, and offer readers a lens through which they can view and understand the complexities of the human experience. Rowling masterfully integrates elements of classical and contemporary mythology into her work, creating a magical tapestry that resonates with readers of all ages.

This research paper seeks to delve into the recreation of mythology within the pages of "Goblet of Fire," examining how Rowling adapts and reinterprets classical myths, folklore, and legends to construct a world that is both familiar and entirely unique. By exploring the symbiotic relationship between mythology and the narrative, we aim to unravel the layers of meaning embedded in the text and shed light on the profound influence of ancient storytelling traditions on

contemporary literature.

The analysis will focus on key mythological elements present in the novel, such as the Triwizard Tournament, the magical creatures featured, and the overarching themes that echo classical myths. Additionally, we will explore the implications of Rowling's mythological adaptations on the development of characters and the broader narrative arc, highlighting the ways in which these elements contribute to the immersive and timeless quality of the "Harry Potter" series. As we embark on this exploration, it becomes evident that Rowling's incorporation of mythology in "Goblet of Fire" goes beyond mere embellishment; it serves as a narrative device that enhances the depth and complexity of the wizarding world, creating a literary masterpiece that resonates not only with fans of fantasy but also with those who appreciate the enduring power of myth.

Review of literature

Wendy Doniger places the characteristic of her article in order to show the series in relation to mythology. The symbol of Harry's power is a scar on his forehead, wherein a lightning bolt is imprinted by the dark lord Voldemort who hit him when he was still a baby and he would have died, but his mother self-sacrificed herself in order to save Harry. The scar connects Voldemort and Harry. Harry Potter has experienced moments of magic where he gets insights of Voldemort's life. The article talks about Harry's school days, his early childhood at the Dursley's, adventures and journey of the story.

In the thesis written by Mellia Hapsari Sbarno, entitled the significance of the Hermione Granger to represent Rowling's school life in Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban she wrote about the resemblance of Hermione Granger with the author J.K Rowling, she compared their physical appearances, their activities and their achievement and quality.

Christel Rumander Kilgarvo (2010) talks about in his thesis *Harry potter and Philosopher's stone*, event character and creature that are relate to Greek mythology, comparing the novel's reference and its mythological equivalents. According to Christel in philosopher's stone there are numerous references to ancient mythologies.

Ardin's research also investigates myth. But the approach used by her is semiological approach with the object of the research is a novel "Red Pyramid". Meanwhile, this research uses the intertextuality as its method approach to identify and analyze the data in the object of the research, which is a novel by J.K. Rowling "*Harry Potter and The Cursed Child*". A thesis by Andi Yeniswari (2009) *The Analysis Mythology in the Novel Harry Potter by J.K.Rowling*. In her thesis she describes the meaning of the mythology contain in Rowling's Harry Potter novel using the myth in pre-modern theories of myth. She Analyzed the story of Harry Potter and limited the range of her research's object into three novels only, they are Harry Potter 1 (*Harry Potter and The Sorcerer's Stone*), Harry Potter 2 (*Harry Potter and The Chamber of Secret*), and Harry Potter 3 (*Harry Potter and The Prisoner of Azkaban*). And in her findings, she found nine data from the whole three series of Harry Potter's story.

Terezie kmochova in his Bachelor paper explain with Celtic myths, legends tradition and rituals analyze their main aspects and compress them with J.K Rowling's book about Harry Potter. He drew the linkage between Celtic tradition and Rowling's books, point out their main interesting aspects and show their resemblance.

Research Methodology

This study employs a qualitative descriptive method. This study is narrative research; therefore, this used qualitative method. Nevertheless, the data of this research are in the form of words. Descriptive method is used to describe the findings of the research.

In this research, there are two types of data, primary and secondary data source. The primary data source is *Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire* novel while the secondary data sources were taken from books, journals, websites, and other materials related to the study

Results and Discussion

The vast array of vivid creatures and fantastical elements that fill the pages and the silver screen of the enthralling, magical world of the Harry Potter franchise were inspired by global, myth, folklore, and legends. For many, the Harry Potter stories were their first introduction to creatures from ancient myth – albeit with a modern twist. Rowling is skilled at fusing elements from some of the world's oldest and greatest legends – tales of heroic journeys, tests of courage and strength, good vs. evil, friendship, love, pain, and heartache, all wrapped up in an enchanted world where nature and magic blend. The familiarity with these elements allows the running themes to be identified, but they are given a new coat of paint. Unicorns, Mer-people, dragons, a sphinx, ghosts, elves, witches, wizards, and giants are among the more famous creatures from classical myth who appear in the story – after all, this is a magical world. However, there are some lesser-known beings who appear, as well as others who played such an important role that it is worth noting how they were adapted from ancient tales into a more modern wizarding world.

Goblet of fire from Celtic mythology

The Goblet of Fire takes center stage in the Triwizard Tournament, a magical competition that brings together wizards from different schools. Its role as the impartial judge and selector of champions adds a layer of mystery and enchantment to the plot. As we delve into its origins and functions, parallels with Celtic mythological motifs begin to emerge, offering a lens through which to appreciate the depth of Rowling's world-building.

Celtic mythology, with its rich tapestry of legends and symbols, often features magical cauldrons imbued with transformative properties. The Cauldron of Inspiration, known in Celtic lore, serves as a source of wisdom, creativity, and rebirth. As we explore the Goblet of Fire, we'll draw connections to these mythical cauldrons, examining how the Goblet acts as a vessel that transforms the destinies of those who dare to approach it.

The structure and challenges of the Triwizard Tournament bear echoes of Celtic rituals and contests. In Celtic tradition, rites and competitions were woven into the fabric of communal life, often serving as tests of bravery and skill. Analyzing the parallels between the Tournament and Celtic practices provides insights into the narrative's cultural depth and the Goblet's role as a conduit for ancient magical energies.

Invisibility from Greek Mythology

In "Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire," invisibility plays a significant role, primarily through the use of the Invisibility Cloak, one of the three Deathly Hallows. This magical artifact allows the wearer to become completely invisible, and it becomes an essential tool for Harry and his friends throughout the series. Here are some connections and thematic resonances between the concept of invisibility in Greek mythology and its manifestation in "Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire"

In Greek mythology, gods often concealed their divine identities to interact with mortals. Similarly, characters in the "Harry Potter" series, particularly Harry himself, use the Invisibility Cloak to conceal their identities and move about without being recognized. This connection reflects a common motif of beings operating in secrecy to achieve their goals. Greek gods would often observe mortals without revealing their presence. Similarly, the Invisibility Cloak allows Harry to move around Hogwarts and other magical places without being seen. This theme of observing and gathering information without being detected aligns with the broader idea of the power of invisibility.

In both Greek mythology and the "Harry Potter" series, the ability to become invisible comes with ethical dilemmas and questions of power. In the myth of Gyges and the Ring of Invisibility, Plato explores the moral implications of acting without being observed. Similarly, characters in "Harry Potter," including Harry, grapple with when and how to use the Invisibility Cloak ethically.

While the specific artifacts or myths may differ between Greek mythology and the "Harry Potter" series, the overarching theme of invisibility as a powerful and morally complex ability is a shared thread. Both traditions explore the consequences and ethical considerations of operating unseen, adding layers of depth to the narrative and raising questions about the nature of power and responsibility.

Veela from Slavic Mythology and Greek Mythology

Veela came from Slavic mythology. They are symbols of wilderness. The favorite activity of Veela is dance. Sometimes people explained circular shaped of darker grass in the fields as being trodden by fairies dancing during the night. According to Slavic they can turn into various animals, but they usually look like maiden and have long hairs, very little clothes and incredible powers. There are different ways veela can come to the world. Veelas were symbols of fatal and unattainable beauty. Veela the image of unimaginably beautiful and dangerous women with long, blond hair has been haunting the imagination of many European cultures throughout history. However, there is a way to take away its powers and kill it.

In Greek mythology nymphs are very similar to Veela their name comes from the same root as the name of Veles. They are described as beautiful, eternally young, dressed in white, with eyes flashing like thunders, and provided with wings. They live in the clouds, in mountain woods or in the waters. They are well-disposed towards men, and they are able to turn themselves into horses, wolves, snakes, falcons and swans. The cult of the Veela was still practiced among South Slavs in the early twentieth century, with offerings of fruits and flowers in caves, cakes near wells, and ribbons hanged to the branches of trees.

Phoenix from Egyptian Mythology, Roman Mythology, Greek Mythology

The Phoenix is a mythical bird that appears in many mythologies from various cultures. The oldest known phoenix is the Egyptian Bennu bird, which is depicted as a falcon or with a heron head. The modern English word *phoenix* entered the English language from Latin, later reinforced by French. The word first entered the English language by way of a borrowing of Latin *phoenīx* into Old English (*fenix*). This borrowing was later reinforced by French influence, which had also borrowed the Latin noun. In time, the word developed specialized use in the English language: For example, the term could refer to an "excellent person" (12th century), a variety of heraldic emblem (15th century), and the name of a constellation (17th century).

The Latin word comes from Greek φοῖνιξ *phoinīx*. The Greek word is first attested in the Mycenaean Greek *po-ni-ke*, which probably meant 'griffin', though it might have meant 'palm tree'. That word is probably a borrowing from a West Semitic word for madder, a red dye made from *Rubia tinctorum*. The word *Phoenician* appears to be from the same root, meaning 'those who work with red dyes'. So, *phoenix* may mean 'the Phoenician bird' or 'the purplish-red bird'.

Giants from Greek Mythology and Norse Mythology

According to the myth Encyclopedia the world giant comes from the Greek Gigantes (meaning earth born). The Giants were the children of Gaia (Mother earth) Famous Greek poet Hesiod state that the parents of the Giant were Gaia and Uranus (Sky). Uranus didn't like his children and instead of letting Gaia give birth. He imprisoned his kids inside of Gaia. The giants were very powerful race. They were large in size. They were half man and half monster. They are four times height of a normal people, and about two meters wide.

Naga from Indian Mythology

In Sanskrit, a *nāgá* (नाग) is a cobra, the Indian cobra (*Naja naja*). A synonym for *nāgá* is *phan* in (फणिन्).. Sometimes the word *nāgá* is also used generically to mean "snake" Nagini is a serpentine goddess from Hindu or Buddhist mythology who is semi divine. Nagas are powerful and beautiful race of half human and half serpent beings who can appear in their different forms. Fully human with snakes on their heads and necks, Ordinary serpents or half –human half –serpent beings. Nagini, Nagin or Nagi is a female form of Naga. Nagini is a two –word from the Sanskrit language.

Naga and Gini. Gini means prince and Naga denotes mythological beats. They are stunningly beautiful serpent princesses. They say their beauty enchants them since it is so wonderful. Anyone who sees them is a mortal. The Nagas are said to live in a magical nether region known as Naga - Loka or Patala Loka. Naga Loka is a kingdom. A gorgeously furnished realm brimming at gems gold and other earthly things. Nagaraj, a mighty Naga lord is in charge of the underground realm. Nagaraja is Known as the Nagas and Naginis king.

Phoenix (Garuda) from Hindu Mythology

The term phoenix, according to etymologists, has roots in the name of the ancient Mediterranean people known as the Phoenicians. In Greek, the word Phoenix refers to a purple – red tint. The Phoenicians were well-known for their purple –red dye. As a result, the Bird’s name comes from the description of its brightly colored feathers. The phoenix is a legendary bird that is thought to have originated in Egypt or the Middle East. Other belief, such as the Greeks, Chinese, Hindus, and others, have mystical bird myths as well. A big bird with flame- colored purple, orange, and gold feathers and a crimson – red breast, the phoenix is described. In addition, it is frequently described as having a long tail and a silver and blued crest of feathers on its head. Stories regarding phoenix – life birds can be found in a variety of civilizations. These mythological birds may share a common ancestor or have very different origins. Historians believe the phoenix was inspired by either the Egyptian avian god Bennu or the mythological Arabian bird the Simurgh. While the origins of the phoenix may never be known, these are some of the myths about this mystical bird that have been passed down through the generations. In Asian mythology, the Chinese Feng Huang or its equivalent, the Japanese Hou-ou, comes closest to a phoenix – like bird. This legendary bird was said to be gorgeous, with the head of a pheasant and the tail of a peacock according to folklore. It did however contain bits from other animals, such as a snake’s neck and a turtle’s back. The sacred bird was supposed to have both male and female characteristics. As a result, in China it symbolizes the Yin-Yang equilibrium, when a righteous ruler is born in Japan, the Hou-ou appears as an auspicious emblem. The phoenix is frequently connected to the avian deity Garuda in Hindu mythology. Garuda, like the phoenix, is a solar bird and serves as the god Vishnu’s mount. He is also represented as having flaming red, orange and yellow colors.

Garuda according to Hindu mythology, attained immortality by selflessness. Snakes had enslaved his mother. Garuda had to embark on an epic mission to acquire a vessel containing amrit, the immortality potion in order to release her. Garuda planned to use the elixir as a ransom for his mother’s release from the snakes. Garuda might have consumed the amrit himself, but he chose not to. Vishnu was so moved by Garuda’s selflessness that he bestowed immortality on him regardless. The phoenix is a potent archetype that represents new beginnings, self – regeneration, and healing. You may already have a close bond with this mythological bird or one may have emerged in your life unexpectedly in the form of art, literature, or another medium. If any case, the phoenix is an auspicious sign for healing and renewal in a particular area of one’s life. The phoenix represents the eternal flame, which in your life might represent faith, will or passion. No matter how many setbacks you face, the phoenix reminds you that the fire and ability to heal and rebirth within you.

Unicorn from Chinese mythology, Japanese mythology and Vietnam Mythology

Asian mythology is rife with tales of magical beings that are very similar to the unicorn of Western mythology. These beings are frequently gentle and benevolent beings with the purest of hearts. Unicorn stories have been collected from all across the world. Deer and horses –like creatures having a single horn in the center of their foreheads. The story of the unicorn in many Asian mythology begins with the claim that it was the first creature created and that it was the most magnificent and pure creature on the planet.

According to legend, an Asian unicorn is a compassionate person that would not harm a fly – literally. Unicorns walked carefully as so not to squash insects. Because of the life within them, they did not consume fruits. When they

ran, their hooves barely touched the grass. This might be related to the Hindu, Buddhist and Jaina concepts of ahimsa, in which one of the major principles is to honor life because all life is holy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the exploration of mythology within J.K. Rowling's "Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire" unveils a nuanced and artfully crafted interplay between contemporary storytelling and ancient mythic elements. Rowling's masterful integration of mythical motifs contributes not only to the richness of the wizarding world but also to the broader cultural and literary landscape. The Triwizard Tournament, conceived as a hero's journey, echoes the timeless narrative structures found in classical mythology, as Harry Potter faces trials, self-discovery, and the inevitable confrontation with dark forces. The inclusion of mythical creatures and magical beings taps into a universal human fascination with the fantastical, grounding the narrative in a tradition that transcends cultural boundaries.

The resurrection of Lord Voldemort serves as a chilling reminder of the archetypal struggle between good and evil, a motif deeply rooted in the mythological underpinnings of storytelling. Themes of friendship and loyalty, exemplified through the unwavering support of Ron and Hermione, reinforce the enduring value of camaraderie—an age-old lesson found in numerous mythic tales.

As this research journey into the mythological dimensions of "Harry Potter and the Goblet of Fire" concludes, it is evident that J.K. Rowling has not only created a captivating narrative for contemporary audiences but has also skillfully tapped into the timeless wellspring of myth. The seamless fusion of modern storytelling and ancient mythological tropes not only enriches the world of Harry Potter but stands as a testament to the enduring power of myth to captivate and inspire across generations. As we close this scholarly exploration, we are reminded that the magic of Rowling's work lies not only in the wizarding spells but in the enchanting echoes of mythology that resonate through the pages of her literary creation.

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